

ECHOES OF STRENGTH AND ELEGANCE: ARTISTIC WORKS DEDICATED TO WOMEN POETS IN AZERBAIJAN LITERATURE

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Abstract

The article talks about artistic works dedicated to our female poets who have great merits in Azerbaijani literature. Our women poets made important contributions to literature not only in terms of poetry and poetic language, but also in ideological, social and cultural terms. In the article, the research and analysis of literary works dedicated to women poets in Azerbaijani literature is carried out, and the issues of the role of women in society are also touched upon. Starting with Mahsati Ganjavi, Khurshidbanu Netavan, Aghabeyim Agha and others have been dedicated to many works and their image has been created. In these works, artistic and poetic approaches to the life of women poets are widely analyzed.

Keywords: Literature, Mahsati, Natavan, Woman, Poet, Work, Image, Culture

When we look at the history of the world, each of us clearly sees the indispensable role and position of women. The role of women in the family and society is great and undeniable. The power of a woman in society is the starting point and foundation of life. Power is not only a physical or political concept. Power is also about the choices people make in life and how they develop at the societal level. Women's power is based on this broad concept. Throughout history, women have been perceived as powerless for various reasons, but over time, women have begun to assert their power in the family, business world, and personal life. Of course, woman is the founder of humanity and society. As in every field, we witness the great work and multifaceted creativity of our women in art and literature. In Azerbaijani literature, the creativity of our female artists plays an important role in the formation of not only literature, but also culture and social life. It is for this reason that attention and interest in our women writers and their creativity has been at a high level.

Today, modern Azerbaijani literature is developing at an increasing pace. (3. p. 16) The main plot line of many works in fiction is the struggle of women. The image of a woman used to appear only in folk literature, folk poetry, fairy tales and epics. Mehsati Ganjavi's literary activity created a new path in Azerbaijani literature, many works were written for him.

Nizami Ganjavi, the author of the first artistic verses about him, highly appreciated his creativity and spirituality in his works. In general, the position of women and their power are widely discussed in the works of Nizami Ganjavi. In literature and art, women are often presented as symbols that combine both strength and elegance.

Among our women poets who combine spiritual and intellectual strength in Azerbaijani literature, but who have a gentle soul and elegance inside, it is worth mentioning the names of Mahsati Ganjavi, Khurshidbanu Netavan, Agabayim Agha, Kamina Khanum, Milvarid Dilbazi, Nigar Rafibeyli, Kamala Aghayeva and others. In literature, works inspired by the creativity of these artists were written and their image was created. Those works combine elegance and literary-artistic power. In the epic "Amir Ahmed and Mahsati", Mirvarid Dilbazi's play "Mahsati", Mammad Said Ordubadi's

novel "Sword and Pen", Nigar Rafibeyli's poem "Mahsati", Kamala Aghayeva's play "Mahsati", Farida Lama's poem "Mahsati", Ilyas Efendiyev's "Khurshidbanu" Natevan" in the play, Huseyn Arif's and Mammad Rahim's play "Natevan" and other artistic works are based on the theme.

In Azerbaijani literature, the image of Mehsati Ganjavi and Khurshidbanu Nateva was created more than our female poets. Mahsati Ganjavi, who is distinguished by his love-themed rubai, has written many works, one of which is the play "Mahsati" by Mirvari Dilbazi (1. p. 12). The verses spoken by Mahsati in the work are very effective.

He says hit the stone with your own hand.

Live without poetry, art, bow.

My problem is the tragedy of womanhood.

This is the rebellious voice of a poet girl. (4. p. 249)

The play describes the events of the time when Mehsati Ganjavi lived. In the work, the poet created a magnificent image of artists of the twelfth century, and most importantly Mahsati Ganjavi, along with images of Nizami, Khagani, Sultan Sanjar, Abul ula, Falaki, Jahangari, Goja, Khatib oglu. The work is based on the notes of love. The injustices of the time and the trampling of women's rights are reflected in the work. The foolish decision of Sultan Sanjar, who believed the words of the hypocritical and cruel vizier and exiled Mehsati from the homeland, also attracts the artistic anger of the reader. In the work, the image of Mahsati reveals the vibrations of the inner world of a loving woman of all eras, who has a gentle heart and is burning with longing for her homeland. In addition to being a lyrical-psychological work, the work also expresses the tragedy of a woman. The plot line of the work is based on the motifs of the epic "Mahsati and Amir Ahmed" and is reminiscent of this epic.

Nigar Rafibeyli's poem "Mahsati" also describes the dark sides of court life and injustices against pure love. The image of Mahsati in the poem reminds of the image of Leyli in Nizami Ganjavi's "Leyli and Majnun". Like Leyli, they want to marry Mahsati to someone whom he does not love.

Eh, if only from this palace, from this luxury

All my life, master, I would be in Iraq!

He is in your desolate, poor house

I would be a lamp burning in sadness. (7. p. 250)

The poem describes Mahsati's troubles with his master Nizami, his hatred for the palace life.

In Mammad Said Ordubadi's work "Sword and Pen", Mahsati is a character depicted by the writer with unique colors. Along with Nizami, the poet devotes a lot of space to the image of Mehsati Ganjavi. Mahsati is one of the perfectly executed female images of the work, whose mind and wisdom are the reflection of a warrior woman reflected in the mirror of that time.

Kamala Aghayeva's poem tragedy "Mahsati", which tells about the life and work of Mehsati Ganjavi, evokes a great impact on the reader as a tragedy of femininity, not of a woman. In the work, the difficult situations that Mahsati fell into, and the internal upheavals are masterfully described. The portraits of Mahsati, Ilyas, Amir Ahmed, Ashraf are portraits of historical figures.

Ilyas, listen up, art world,

It is like an eye to see the world.

I hate those palaces

Where are the palaces of my free heart? (5. p. 13)

As can be seen from the verses, the spirit of the people and the inner world of Mahsati Ganjavi come to life in parallel.

Many works have been written about Khurshidbanu Natavan, known as Khan's daughter, and her character has been revived. The sound of Natava's innovations in his homeland, the work he did with pleasure and enthusiasm spread far and wide (6. p. 15). "Khurshidbanu Natavan", one of the most famous works of I. Efendiyev, tells about the life of Khurshidbanu Natavan, a well-known poet and a symbol of his people's struggle, who lived in the city of Shusha in the late 18th and early 19th centuries. The main theme of the work is taken from the life of poetess Khurshidbanu

Nateva, the daughter of Karabakh Khan Mehdiqulu Khan. I. Efendiyev brought the idea of destiny, freedom and unity of the people to the fore in the example of historical events and created the image of a perfect woman.

These words from his mouth are very effective. Also tell us that Azerbaijan, which has found its national unity and freedom, is waiting for us at the end of these steep roads (2. p. 241.). As the main image of the work, the main ideas that the writer wants to convey to the reader are revealed in the example of Nateva's personal life and social activities. The author described Khan's daughter as a noble woman who found wide fame. The character of Natevan is widely presented and the struggle is covered in depth.

As in works of art, the power of women has a positive effect not only on their surroundings, but also on the development of society as a whole. These images simultaneously bring to life the strength and elegance of women.

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